

Cites	Authors	Title	DOI	Relevant title?	Duplicate?	Excluded?	Relevant Abstract?
101	NS Mauthner, O	Open access digital data sharing: Principles, policies and practices	10.1080/02691728.2012.760663	1	FALSE		1
33	A Abella, M Ortiz	The process of open data publication and reuse	10.1002/asi.24116	1	FALSE		1
31	DJ Conrado, MO	Open innovation: Towards sharing of data, models and workflows	10.1016/j.ejps.2017.06.035	1	FALSE		1
10	M Lnenicka, H Kl	Big and open linked data analytics: a study on changing roles and skills in the higher e	10.1186/s41239-020-00208-z	1	FALSE		1
10	JR Crusoe, K Ahl	Users' activities for using open government data—a process framework	10.1108/TG-04-2019-0028	1	FALSE		1
9	J Kim	Overview of disciplinary data sharing practices and promotion of open data in science	10.6087/kcse.149	1	FALSE		1
8	D Wang, D Riche	An analysis of interaction between users and open government data portals in data ac	10.1007/978-3-319-97289-3_14	1	FALSE		1
2	N Morelli	Open data: creating communities and practices for a new common	10.1007/978-3-319-77547-0_10	1	FALSE		1
2	L Zhang, RR Dov	A review of open research data policies and practices in China	10.5334/dsj-2021-003	1	FALSE		1
0	M Tejada, D Torr	A user-centered process for the analysis and visualization of open data sets		1	FALSE		1
0	A Bumann, R Tei	Predicting the spread of invasive marine species with open data and machine learning: Process and Challenges		1	FALSE		1
92	P Missier, SS Sa	Janus: From Workflows to Semantic Provenance and Linked Open Data	10.1007/978-3-642-17819-1_16	1	FALSE		0
24	L Peer, A Green	Building an open data repository for a specialized research community: Process, challenges and lessons		1	FALSE		0
23	F Cifuentes-Silva	Towards an architecture and adoption process for linked data technologies in open go	10.1145/2063518.2063529	1	FALSE		0
19	MR Karim, A Micl	Improving data workflow systems with cloud services and use of open data for bioinformatics research		1	FALSE		0
14	A Berro, I Megdic	A content-driven ETL processes for open data	10.1007/978-3-319-10518-5_3	1	FALSE		0
6	C Lee, S Allard, F	Open data meets digital curation: An investigation of practices and needs		1	FALSE		0
4	P Poinet, D Stefa	Collaborative Workflows and Version Control Through Open-Source and Distributed C	10.1007/978-3-030-51295-8_18	1	FALSE		0
1	A Koch, KC Glov	Open-data practices and challenges among early-career paleo-researchers		1	FALSE		0
1	JR Beluzo, B Dia	Re-Public: workflow to publish and reuse Linked Open Government Data	10.1145/3466933.3466943	1	FALSE		0
0	A Beshiri, J Mita,	Best Practices of Consuming Linked Open Data		1	FALSE		0
0	A Vilela, A Almei	OpenData Processor: An Automation tool for the process of extracting and publishing open data to CKAN		1	FALSE		0
0	C Di Ciccio, JD F	Improving the usability of Open Data portals from a business process perspective		1	FALSE		0
0	A Kitamoto	FAIRness for Citizens: Workflow and Platform for Open Data with a Case Study on Edo Cooking Recipes		1	FALSE		0
25	M d'Aquin	On the use of Linked Open Data in education: Current and future practices	10.1007/978-3-319-30493-9_1	1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
25	M Fioretti	Open Data: Emerging trends, issues and best practices		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
2	O Gorlitz, G Grom	The Open Data Workflow: Towards an Open Data Middleware		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
2	J Li, L Zhang	Open research data policies and practices in China		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
1	N Morelli, A De G	Open data as new commons: Design strategies to support the creation of communities	10.4324/9780429022746-15/open-data-new-commons	1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
1	CA Hasenkopf	Sharing Lessons-Learned on Effective Open Data, Open-Source Practices from OpenAQ, a Global Open Air Quality Community.		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
1	ML Zeng, M Hlav	Standards and best practices related to the publication, exchange and usage of open	10.1002/pra2.2017.14505401086	1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
0	SE Bond, P Dille	Linked Open Data for the Ancient Mediterranean: Structures, Practices, Prospects		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
0	T Oefelein	Delivering on open data: Current practices in data sharing, and challenges ahead!		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
0	J Jarke	Open Government Data Practices: The Example of Civic Hacking		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
0	A Ruckstuhl, K S	What we Learned About the Data Science Life Cycle: Best Practices and Open Research Challenges		1	FALSE	Not peer-reviewed journal	
0	V Brussa, J Gerke	Social Big Data: challenges of open governments and collaborative processes in the construction of data. The case of health sector and its		1	FALSE	Language not spoken	
4	CE Kronkosky, B	Improved oil recovery estimation with data analytic methods: A workflow for open data analysis		1	TRUE		
26	L De Vocht, A Dir	A visual exploration workflow as enabler for the exploitation of linked open data		1	TRUE		
15	MB Kjærgaard, C	Current practices and infrastructure for open data based research on occupant-centric design and operation of buildings		1	TRUE		
5	S Park, JR Gil-G	Open data innovation: Visualizations and process redesign as a way to bridge the transparency-accountability gap		1	TRUE		
2	JO Hodonu-Wusi	Malaysian researchers on open data: The first national survey on awareness, practices and attitudes		1	TRUE		
1	B Cleland, B Gall	Configuration processes in open data		1	TRUE		
1	S Rosim, JR de F	Open data practices: The case of south america drainage datasets		1	TRUE		

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0	CP Mandeville, V	Open data practices among users of primary biodiversity data			1	TRUE	
62	E Ruijter, A Meijer	Open government data as an innovation process: Lessons from a living lab experim	10.1080/15309576.2019.1568884		1	TRUE	
14	D Johansson, J L	Mobile e-services and open data in e-government processes: Transforming citizen inv	10.1145/2837185.2837197		1	TRUE	
5	D Villa	Crowdsourced heritage tourism open-data, small-data and e-participatory practices a	10.1007/978-3-319-15859-4_19		1	TRUE	
1	W Izdebski, A Zw	Open data in spatial data infrastructure: the practices and experiences of Poland	10.1080/17538947.2021.1952323		1	TRUE	
11	M Hartog, B Mulc	Open data within governmental organisations: effects, benefits and challenges of the implementation process				FALSE	
10	E Styrin, LF Lunz	Open data and open government: From abstract principles to institutionalized practice	10.1145/2912160.2912161			FALSE	
9	A Berro, I Megdic	Graph-based etl processes for warehousing statistical open data				FALSE	
8	EE Fink	American Art Collaborative (AAC) Linked Open Data (LOD) Initiative, Overview and Recommendations for Good Practices				FALSE	
1	FA Zeleti, A Ojo	Agile mechanisms for open data process innovation in public sector organizations: To	10.1145/3326365.3326387			TRUE	
0	RFS Meiling	Research on the Value-added Process and Mechanism of Government Open Data Based on Value Chain Theory				FALSE	
0	CY Liu, WP Li, Y	Privacy Perils of Open Data and Data Sharing: A Case Study of Taiwan's Open Data Policy and Practices				FALSE	
0	K Kim, K Lee	Towards Ingestion Processes of Komsat Data in Open Data Cube on Open Source Cloud Computing Environment				FALSE	
0	E Karoune	Pre-print of data paper for assessing open science practices in phytolith research.				FALSE	
55	I Mergel, A Kleibr	Open data outcomes: US cities between product and process innovation				FALSE	
29	JD Gezelter	Open source and open data should be standard practices	10.1021/acs.jpcclett.5b00285			FALSE	
28	X Masip-Bruin, G	Unlocking the value of open data with a process-based information platform				FALSE	
21	IG Johnson, A Pu	Neighbourhood data: Exploring the role of open data in locally devolved policymaking	10.1145/3274352			TRUE	
14	T Tossavainen, S A	linked open data based system utilizing structured open innovation process for addr	10.1007/s10489-015-0704-8			FALSE	
12	JE Raffaghelli, S	Is there a social life in open data? The case of open data practices in educational technology research				FALSE	
11	B Otjacques, M S	Open data visualization keeping traces of the exploration process	10.1145/2422604.2422612			FALSE	
7	A Schulz, S Döw	Integrating process modeling and linked open data to improve decision making in disaster management				FALSE	
7	S Laine, C Lee, M	Transparent data supply for open information production processes				FALSE	
7	KW Chen, LK No	Workflow for generating 3D urban models from open city data for performance-based urban design				FALSE	
6	M Currie	The Data-fication of Openness The Practices and Policies of Open Government Data in Los Angeles				FALSE	
5	HH Ahmed	Data quality assessment in the integration process of linked open data (LOD)				FALSE	
2	K Baždarić, I Vrki	Attitudes and practices of open data, preprinting, and peer-review—A cross sectional study on Croatian scientists				FALSE	
100	S Kubler, J Robe	Comparison of metadata quality in open data portals using the Analytic Hierarchy Process				FALSE	
71	A Zuideerwijk, M J	Design principles for improving the process of publishing open data	10.1108/TG-07-2013-0024			TRUE	
39	J Kucera, D Chla	Methodologies and Best Practices for Open Data Publication.				FALSE	
35	OA Zarate, JG Bi	Balancing benefits and risks of immortal data: participants' views of open consent in th	10.1002/hast.523			TRUE	
23	T Dhu, G Giuliani	National open data cubes and their contribution to country-level development policies and practices				FALSE	
21	E Bannier, G Bar	The Open Brain Consent: Informing research participants and obtaining consent to sh	10.1002/hbm.25351			FALSE	
17	RE Timme, WJ V	Optimizing open data to support one health: Best practices to ensure interoperability c	10.1186/s42522-020-00026-3			FALSE	
16	F Huettmann	... , and public open access and open source code in (tropical) research: the Rio con	10.1007/978-1-4939-2208-6_16			FALSE	
12	E Castro, M Cros	Evaluating and promoting open data practices in open access journals	10.3138/jsp.49.1.66			FALSE	
10	S Hunnius, B Kri	The social shaping of open data through administrative processes	10.1145/2641580.2641601			TRUE	
10	D Garijo, Y Gil	Towards open publication of reusable scientific workflows: Abstractions, standards, and linked data				FALSE	
9	T Enders, C Ben	How to implement an open data strategy? Analyzing organizational change processes to enable value creation by revealing data				FALSE	
8	D Johansson, J L	Mobile e-services and open data in e-government processes-concept and design	10.1007/978-3-319-23144-0_14			FALSE	
7	YN Chen	A review of practices for transforming library legacy records into linked open data	10.1007/978-3-319-70863-8_12			FALSE	
7	G Ducci	Public communication in the Processes of Transparency and Accountability in the Era of Open Data				FALSE	

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7	A Gaignard, H S	From Scientific Workflow Patterns to 5-star Linked Open Data.			FALSE		
7	A Luthfi, M Janss	A Framework for Analyzing How Governments Open Their Data: Institution, Technology, and Process Aspects Influencing Decision-Making			FALSE		
6	S Carbon, R Cha	A measure of open data: a metric and analysis of reusable data practices in biomedic	10.1101/282830.abstract		FALSE		
5	D Corrales-Gara	A research agenda on open data impact process for open innovation			FALSE		
5	N Morelli, A Götz	A system of innovation to activate practices on open data: The Open4Citizens project	10.1007/978-3-319-92022-1_9		FALSE		
5	P Schmitz, E Fra	Linked open data and e-participation in the EU law-making process	10.1007/978-3-319-44159-7_6		FALSE		
4	EM Nilsson	The smell of urban data: Urban archiving practices beyond open data			FALSE		
4	RD Triviño	State of open government data as a process in Ecuador			FALSE		
3	S Campus, R Sc	The open data kit suite, a mobile data collection technology as an opportunity for forest mensuration practices			FALSE		
3	SP Mehdiabadi, A	Explicit jet veto as a tool to purify the underlying event in the Drell–Yan process using	10.1088/1361-6471/ab33a9		TRUE		
3	F Izzzi, GL Scalet	Enhancing the spatial dimensions of open data: Geocoding open PA information using	10.1007/978-3-642-39646-5_45		FALSE		
3	L Meggiolaro, S	... people, sharing knowledge, increasing transparency: Using the land portal to increase access to open data, share best practices and monitor women's lar			FALSE		
3	VL Castro	Web Semantico e Linked Open Data: best practices, prospettive e criticità			FALSE		
3	CS Albano, LB D	Publishing Data in Open Format: Formalizing the Process in a Brazilian Federal Unive	10.1145/2910019.2910059		FALSE		
3	BE Penteadado, JC	Methodologies for publishing linked open government data on the web: a systematic mapping and a unified process model			FALSE		
3	RR Gutierrez, A I	Towards adopting open and data-driven science practices in bed form dynamics rese	10.1002/esp.4811		FALSE		
3	SDK Tomic, A Fe	agriopenlink: Towards adaptive agricultural processes enabled by open interfaces, lin	10.1007/978-3-319-03437-9_39		FALSE		
2	JX Chen, MZ Re	Learning processes based on data sources with certainty levels in linked open data			FALSE		
2	EM Nilsson, V W	Urban Archiving for Smarter Cities: Archival Practices beyond Open Data			FALSE		
2	J Thomas	Best Practices in the Implementation of Open Data at a Municipal Government Level			FALSE		
2	K Schleicher	Open Data/Open Source: Seismic Unix scripts to process a 2D land line			FALSE		
2	B Penteadado, MJ	Process model with quality control for the production of high quality linked open government data			FALSE		
2	E Karoune	Data from "Assessing Open Science Practices in Phytolith Research"			FALSE		
2	L Bishop	Reply to: Natasha Mauthner and Odette Parry's "Open access digital data sharing: principles, policies and practices"			FALSE		
1	EJ Momo, S De f	Addressing management practices of private forests by remote sensing and open data: A tentative procedure			FALSE		
1	F Wiyani, MEWA	ANALYSIS STUDY OF OPEN DATA IMPLEMENTATION TO IMPROVE PUBLIC POLICY MAKING PROCESS IN JAKARTA PROVINCIAL GOVERNMENT .			FALSE		
1	D Jovanović	USE OF OPEN DATA AND APPLICATIONS IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS			FALSE		
1	P Carli, V Dessi	Design strategies to improve water resilience in urban areas. Good practices for an open-data culture of the urban environment			FALSE		
1	L Penev, T Georg	The Pensoft data publishing workflow: The FAIRway from articles to Linked Open Data			FALSE		
1	M Krumova	Knowledge Creation and Sharing Process Enhanced by Cloud-Based Tools, Anno-tation Technology and Open Data			FALSE		
1	M Janssen, J Ub	Towards generalized process patterns for detecting corruption within the government	10.1145/3209281.3209282		FALSE		
1	E Sall, LLC Urba	Making Open Transportation Data Useful and Accessible: Recommendations for Good Practices in 2 Open Data Standards Management. 3			FALSE		
1	C Boisvert, K Do	An Open Workflow Environment to Support Learning Data Science			FALSE		
1	A Syarif, MA Sal	A Comparative Analysis of Open Government Data in Several Countries: The Practice	10.1007/978-3-030-36056-6_33		FALSE		
1	MS Taslimi, M Sa	Identify and Prioritize the Challenges of Achieving the Open Government Data Policy (OGDP): Application of the Analytic Hierarchy Process and Fuzzy TOP			FALSE		
1	L Quingerski, D M	ETL Process Using Open Data From E-Gov For Discovery And Knowledge Representation			FALSE		
1	G Vancauwenbei	Governance and performance of open spatial data policies in Europe: What can we learn from the INSPIRE Reporting Process?			FALSE		
1	PER Salas, KK E	StdTrip: An a Priori Design Approach and Process for Publishing Open Government Data.			FALSE		
1	MA Lawrence-Ku	Beyond the Paywall: Examining Open Access and Data Sharing Practices Among Faculty at Virginia Tech Through the Lens of Social Exchange			FALSE		
1	E Bassolino, V D	Data Exchange Processes for the Definition of Climate-Proof Design Strategies for the Adaptation to Heatwaves in the Urban Open Spaces of Dense Italian			FALSE		
0	S Salem, F Benc	LODQuMa: A Free-ontology process for Linked (Open) Data quality management			FALSE		
0	GV Anupama, R	Data warehousing for Open Data sharing and decision support in agriculture: a case s	10.1007/s41870-020-00494-w		FALSE		

Cites	Authors	Title	DOI	Relevant title?	Duplicate?	Excluded?	Relevant Abstract?
0	S Li, Y Chen	Research on the Decision-Making Process of Civil Servant Resisting Open Data Base	10.1007/978-3-030-71305-8_20		FALSE		
0	GT Luu, I Lizama	TIMSCONVERT: A workflow to convert trapped ion mobility data to open data formats	10.1101/2021.12.09.472024.abstract		FALSE		
0	CC Ma, TM Yang	Exploring Government Officials' Data Collection Process in Open Data Initiatives			FALSE		
0	T Stein	Investigation of the efficiency of work processes within a farm using open data			FALSE		
0	Y Tzitzikas, M Pit	What Process a University can Follow for Open Data? The University of Crete Case			FALSE		
0	A Kanematsu, M	Proposals and practices for regional resource revitalization for tourism promotion by promoting citizens' health and open data promotion			FALSE		
0	I Zinchenko, O O	Influence of the materials in the format of «open data» on the process of evaluation of scientific research			FALSE		
0	MC Praetzellis, J	The FAIR Island Project: Advancing Optimal Open Data Policies and Practices			FALSE		
0	R Büno Heslinga	Improving social housing in a sea of open data: The potential role of open data in the decision-making process regarding the energetic improvement by hous			FALSE		
0	M Zandstra, A Az	Open research, open data, and your development organization: best practices in information and data management for development			FALSE		
0	C Bakker, S Huni	Ethical and Practical Considerations of Open Data Sharing when Conducting Research with Human Participants			FALSE		
0	M Keränen	Knowledge processes and information quality in open data context: conceptual considerations and empirical findings			FALSE		
0	VA Omoniyi, GL I	Big Data Technology And Leveraging Open Data For Electoral Processes In Nigeria			FALSE		
0	M Donnelly	An analysis of national open data and open science policies in Europe: process and findings			FALSE		
0	J Behnke, H Ran	Practices in NASA's EOSDIS to Promote Open Data and Research Integrity			FALSE		
0	J Łukowicz, A Iwa	Identification of events and processes in Linked Open Data generated from SDI resources			FALSE		
0	S CIUFFREDA	Towards an ontology-based, open data exchange format for interoperability in BIM processes			FALSE		
0	T Myers, J Treva	Linking people, processes and open data automatically to enhance tropical research on sustainability			FALSE		
0	B Lane, I Garous	An open web-based module developed to advance data-driven hydrologic process le	10.1002/hyp.14273		TRUE		
0	R Chawuthai	Linked Open Data-based Knowledge Management Process for Biodiversity			FALSE		
0	AJ Sánchez-Pad	WITHDRAWN: Notes Meeting CONTRIBUTION. Open data in the digital transformation process of the agri-food, forestry and rural sectors.			FALSE		
0	ME Cook	Open Data Planning Activities: Emerging Practices from a Public Value Approach			FALSE		
0	N Kikuchi, LY Tra	KU-ORCAS Digital Humanities Project of Kansai University and the Process of Open Data Nobuhiko Kikuchi			FALSE		
0	C Shen, MG Fra	Non-invasive acquisition of fetal ECG from the maternal xyphoid process: a feasibility	10.1088/1361-6579/aaaaa4		FALSE		
0	MJ Han, A Kinnai	... Data for Digitized Special Collections, White paper# 1: Transforming special collections metadata into linked open data: mappings, entity reconciliation, w			FALSE		
0	I Kramer	... renovation of residential real estate and neighbourhoods: An exploratory research into the possibilities of open data to support the renovation process in tl			FALSE		
0	Y Choi, B Chudd	Open Data Analytics using Fuzzy Cognitive Map (FCM) Approach for Decision Making Process in Public Sector			FALSE		
0	H Savoy, DPC P	Harnessing the Power of Open Data and Analytics for Characterizing the Role of Hydrological Processes in the Spread of a Vector-borne Livestock Disease			FALSE		
0	K Tarabanis, T El	Deliverable 2.2: Open Data learning processes and analytics			FALSE		
0	K Hansson, A Da	Open research data repositories: Practices, norms, and metadata for sharing images	10.1002/asi.24571		FALSE		
0	A Correa	A Collaborative Approach to Support Document Structuring Process in the Context of Open Government Data			FALSE		
0	C Fabry, A Pittne	Recommendations for an Open Science approach to welding process research data	10.1007/s40194-021-01151-x		FALSE		
0	CM Gough, C Gi	NEON Data in the Classroom: An Open Education Resource for Enhancing Understanding of Terrestrial Carbon Cycling Processes Across Scales			FALSE		
0	CM Pereira, E Fe	Analysis of the information retrieval process in databases published as linked open data using the RDB2LOD approach			FALSE		
0	S Rautenberg, A	A workflow for sharing primary data as Linked Open Data			FALSE		
0	J Jarke	Open government data practices: Producing 'open publics' through civic hacking			FALSE		
0	JJSB Lin	The role of open government data in Boston's climate adaptation process			FALSE		
0	SG Barsanti, SG	Preface: Proceedings of ArcheoFOSS XIII Workshop—Open Software, Hardware, Processes, Data and Formats in Archaeological Research			FALSE		
0	B Lane, I Garous	Better understanding of hydrologic process through data-driven learning facilitated by	10.22541/au.161647873.37465866		FALSE		
0	M Térmens Grae	Good practices and strategic recommendations on exchange formats applicable to the Registry Service for Libraries and Related Organizations (SERBER) i			FALSE		
0	S Stall, K Lehner	Earth and Space Sciences Data Are a World Heritage—Community Partnership to Dev	10.1002/essoar.10500012.1		FALSE		
0	S Lewis	Paving the way to open and interoperable research data service workflows			FALSE		

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0	A Whyte, R Macr	Paving the way to open and interoperable research data service workflows			FALSE		
0	M Clementi	GED-TOOLKIT: Open Geospatial Data and Tools to support Generative Economy Processes in local communities			FALSE		
0	R Caillet, A Rang	2021 State of Open at the University of Colorado Boulder: An Update on Open Access Practices Based on Data from 2020			FALSE		
0	Y Fukami	Open and Clarified Process of Compatibility Standards for Promoting Data Exchange	10.1007/s12626-021-00087-4		FALSE		
0	S Labelle, JB Le	Distribution Methods and Documentary Processes, Conditions of "Detachment" of Public Information: Analysis of Legislative Discussions and Regional Oper			FALSE		
0	R Zakariya	... literature study research, researchers conducted data collection to be able to explain the importance of using Open Government through open data initiati			FALSE		